
Sustaining Forests and the People: Learning from Indigenous Forest Management as Social Forestry in the Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The growth of social forestry as a participatory forest management approach with the goals of conservation, social equity, and economic viability is evident in developing countries where indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLCs) rely on forests for livelihood. This comparative exploratory case study analyzed the social forestry elements of two indigenous forest management (IFM) and two non-IFM cases in the Philippines guided by the Social Forestry Framework of Rebugio (1995). Thematic analysis of key informant interviews and focus group discussions was conducted, supplemented by a review of relevant scientific literature and documents. IFM and non-IFM cases demonstrated elements of social forestry. They were similar in terms of utilizing agroforestry and diversifying livelihoods. The IFM cases differed in the formal organization and integration of the Kalahan case into mainstream institutions compared to the Ifugao *muyong*, resulting in positive and negative implications. The more complex institutional

arrangements in the non-IFM cases add to challenges in forest management but also help ensure accountability. IFM and non-IFM systems can learn from each other through formal and informal learning exchanges that can facilitate a culture of support across different forest management strategies. Results indicate that IFM can enrich innovation in social forestry practice through indigenous values such as a deep personal connection with nature and collectivist worldviews embedded in indigenous knowledge systems and practices, especially amid increasing recognition of the role of IPLCs in biodiversity conservation. Further in-depth studies are recommended to analyze the effectiveness of IFM and non-IFM practices in meeting social forestry goals.

Keywords: Culture, forest, indigenous peoples, participatory forest management, social forestry

INTRODUCTION

Social forestry diversified the lenses of forest science, evolving from its initial focus to address the biological limitations of forests, specifically trees, to provisions for socio-economic issues, to strengthening local institutions, including customary laws, and now, to endeavoring the nations' states for robust forest policy creation and implementation (Asmin et al., 2019). Social forestry encompasses all forms of forestry interventions engaging local communities in the harmonization of the dynamic interrelationship among the community, the state, and the biophysical environment (Dove, 1995). As such, social forestry may be in the form of agroforestry, farm forestry, or community forestry.

The discipline gained prominent global attention from 1977 to 1986 when approximately 60% of the forestry lending from landbank due for projects and programs amounting to 1.3 million US dollars were devoted to social forestry to what was then defined as "forestry for local community development" (Gregersen et al., 1989; Song et al., 2021). Based on the statistics, Kortén (1994) reported that social forestry lending has a large-scale significant increase from only 5% in

the previous decade. Anthropologists believe that the lack of tenurial security has led to practices detrimental to forest health, which is the reason why community participation is now being sought as seen as a driver of sustainable forest management; this is particularly done by providing more support, both financial and technical, to social forestry programs worldwide and ensure tenurial security through the creation of different policies (Schnurr and Holtz, 1998; Song et al., 2021).

In the Philippines, the social forestry objectives revolve around the concepts of preventing forest deterioration, ensuring not equal but equitable access to various ecosystem services, and sustainable management of finite forest resources (Asmin et al., 2019; Pulhin et al., 2007; Rebugio et al., 2010). To realize these objectives, social forestry has become part of the country's path toward sustainable forest resources management encapsulating three major systems, namely state-initiated social forestry programs, local government-led social forestry programs, and traditional or indigenous forest management initiatives (Asmin et al., 2019; Hlaing et al., 2013; Pulhin et al., 2007;; Rebugio et al., 2010; Suharjito, 2009). To further illustrate, state-initiated social forestry programs are being implemented through contract-based social forestry programs. In contrast, the local government-led and the indigenous and/or traditional forest management initiatives are implemented through co-management and self or community initiatives, respectively (Asmin et al., 2019; Hlaing et al., 2013;; Rebugio et al., 2010).

This paper explored four forest management initiatives representing indigenous and non-indigenous social forestry programs in the Philippines. The study objectives are: 1) Describe selected cases of indigenous forest management and social forestry interventions in the Philippines; and 2) Compare the selected cases based on Rebugio's social forestry framework. Generally, it aimed to analyze and compare selected cases to improve social forestry applications in the Philippines. The analysis was based largely on secondary data captured at different periods but still representative of the case contexts.

METHODOLOGY

The comparative exploratory case study research design was used. The social forestry cases were purposively selected to represent diversity in social forestry initiatives based on previous research and extension activities of the Department of Social Forestry and Forest Governance-College of Forestry and Natural Resources, University of the Philippines Los Baños (DSSFG-CFNR, UPLB). The cases are as follows:

- two indigenous forest management sites (Kalahan Educational Foundation and *muyong* system in Ifugao), and
- two non-indigenous forest management sites (Barobbob Watershed Occupants Association and Federation of Vista Hills, Kalongkong, and Kakilingan Upland Farmers Association, Inc.).

Primary and secondary data were gathered and analyzed. Primary data were obtained through key informant interviews (KII) and observation. In contrast, secondary data were based on related literature available online via open access or institutional subscription, with emphasis on scientific journal articles and available project reports. Thematic analysis of data was done using the Framework for Social Forestry as a Development Program (Rebugio, 1985).

The Framework for Social Forestry as a Development program by Rebugio (1985) contains basic elements that are most likely to be applicable to social forestry initiatives, whether traditional/indigenous or interventionist. The framework focused on the six interconnected, interdependent, and interacting elements of the framework, namely environment, targets, goals and objectives, technology, agency, and impacts (Figure 1). Impacts were analyzed based on the LIFE (livelihood, income, forest condition, and equity) indicators following Hashiguchi et al. (2016).

Figure 1

Framework of Social Forestry as a Development Program (Rebugio, 1985)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Indigenous Forest Management: *Muyong* system of Ifugao and the Kalahan Educational Foundation (KEF)

Context

The biophysical and socio-economic contexts of the KEF and Ifugao are very similar, if not practically the same. Both share similar biophysical landscapes, considering that their areas are forested mountains. Their indigeneity and traditional roots are also close. Both had a history of being oppressed and discriminated against, and their ancestral lands were grabbed either by the government or by some greedy individuals and business multinational corporations. Many of their forest areas need to be rehabilitated after so many years of degradation and misuse/abuse. However, there are some divergences when it comes to their contexts. KEF was able to use its culture and tried to mainstream and institutionalize it by putting up an academy as one of KEF's projects. They use their age-old traditions to do agroforestry and other planting and harvesting methods. Their innovative use of wild fruits to establish the fruit processing industry is distinct. Meanwhile, the Ifugao focused on the *muyong* system of managing the forests embedded within the Ifugao rice terraces (IRT) integrated agricultural system.

Targets

The direct targets in both IFMs are mainly the indigenous peoples in the communities - the *Ikalahan* and the *Ifugao*.

These are located within ancestral domains legally recognized by the government through the Indigenous Peoples Rights Act (IPRA). The resource system, which essentially includes forests and other natural resources, is also a direct target. The direct targets are an important basis for the objectives and goals of social forestry initiatives. Secondary targets are other stakeholders within the community, including non-IPs.

Goals and Objectives

The goals and objectives of KEF are forest protection and rehabilitation, while in Ifugao, it is sustainable and self-sufficiency. Both have a livelihood component that is forest-dependent and includes subsistence. Being forest-dependent, biodiversity protection and enhancement are part of the IFM systems studied.

Technology

In terms of forest-related technologies, Ifugao and KEF are not that different as both communities incorporate traditional knowledge. Specifically, there is the Forest Improvement Technology or FIT of the *Ikalahan* and the *muyong* of the Ifugao. The FIT is a technology developed by the *Ikalahan* elders; as such, this technology sprung from *Ikalahan*'s traditional practices and basically counts as timber stand improvement in silviculture. This practice can be a production and a conservation technology as the main purpose is to improve forest health by clearing damaged trees for lumber (Rice, D. 2001). It involves forest stand thinning and the harvesting of felled trees for potential timber and lumber for the community's use. The *muyong*, on the other hand, is a traditional forestry system of the Ifugaos where silviculture and agroforestry are incorporated. It incorporates Assisted Natural Regeneration, which includes enrichment planting and several stand management techniques. It is also a tree-based agroforestry involving multiple cropping in their swidden areas. Similar to the FIT of the KEF, the *muyong* system may count as both production and conservation technology as it involves stand improvement techniques, whilst harvest is based on private ownership of these *muyong* lands. In this method, selective harvesting is observed for the efficient and regulated

whole-tree harvesting for timber. Both technologies emanate from indigenous knowledge and traditions. They are the primary forestry systems in the said communities that have proven successful and sustainable over time.

Table 1

Comparison of Social Forestry Technologies in Ifugao and KEF

KEF	Ifugao
Forest Improvement Technology (FIT)	<i>Muyong</i>
Timber Stand Improvement	Assisted Natural Regeneration
Traditional Silvicultural Method	Tree-based Agroforestry
Forest stand thinning and harvesting of felled trees for timber and lumber.	Selective harvesting; Efficient & regulated whole-tree harvesting for timber
Ecological Niche	IRT or <i>ala/alahan</i>

Agency

In terms of agency, the KEF and Ifugao are also very similar, specifically in human resources, and follow traditions. The only difference is that there is an organization that is responsible for the management of the Kalahan Reserve in Imugan, Nueva Vizcaya, is the Kalahan Educational Foundation, while in Ifugao, management is based on family lineage ownership or private ownership of lands. Since authority and responsibilities are decentralized in the management of the Kalahan Reserve, the Kalahan Educational Foundation becomes the principal implementing agency of the social forestry initiatives within the said environment, which is spearheaded mostly by their selected tribal elders along Ikalahan communities. The power devolved to the Ikalahans in resource management enables them to

formulate and decide on their policies in the management efforts. In Ifugao, on the other hand, the regulation and management of their *muyong* forest lands are the responsibility of their owners or family members. Moreover, both communities follow customary laws, specifically for KEF, and there is that of the *tong-tongan* system, which they use to resolve forest violations. At the same time, this is also true for Ifugao; most of the customary laws are parallel and connected with mainstream institutions and programs.

Table 2

Comparison of Social Forestry Agency in Ifugao and KEF

KEF	Ifugao
<p>Managed by the KEF</p> <p>Resource management is handled by KEF but is aided by Forest Guards and concerned BLGUs in policy monitoring and implementation.</p> <p>Follows customary laws (<i>Tong-tongan system</i>) and community-developed policies.</p> <p>Human Resources refers to Ikalahans.</p>	<p>Owned and managed by family (private)</p> <p>Resource management partly shared by community members allows them to gather resources in the <i>muyong</i></p> <p>Governed mainly by customary laws within mainstream institutions and programs</p> <p>Included in the IRT-GIAHS</p>

Impacts

The similarities in elements of social forestry for both communities generated similar impacts. Initially, there were improvements in local livelihoods; for KEF, there is that of the ecological niches, forest management, and the fruit processing niche that had employed many of its members, while in Ifugao, there is that of the ensured water improvement and supply that greatly aided the irrigation of their agricultural systems, and the increase of timber supply for potential wood carving initiatives. The diversification of livelihoods and improvements in ecological services had basically invited several alternatives for income for

both communities as well. In line with this, there are also evident improvements in terms of forest health and biodiversity in terms of wild flora and fauna, as well as overall forest health. Lastly, regarding equity, both communities have now been sustaining equal distributions and recognition of rights as well as collective labor regardless of social status.

Further, with the application and empowerment of culture and traditions injected into the forestry system today, there was enrichment in IKSP along with the promotion of culture, which is evident for both communities. In addition, the increase in income helped the Ikalahans to suffice for food security and health, along with the diversification of crops and medicinal sources for Ifugao. Lastly, aside from the improvements in forest conditions and biodiversity, there were also developments in overall environmental quality, specifically on watershed health and carbon security for KEF. At the same time, Ifugao is seeing water, air, and soil quality improvement.

Table 3

Comparison of Impacts of the Social Forestry System in Ifugao and KEF

Theme	KEF	Ifugao
<i>Livelihoods</i>	Regulated local use of and access to forests; Developed opportunities for livelihood (food processing) and employed members.	Ensured water quantity & quality for agriculture; Increased timber supply for wood carving.
<i>Income</i>	Increased income from livelihood diversification (ecological niches)	Increased income from wood carving & agri
<i>Forest Condition</i>	Recognized with less deforestation; Improved forest health and biodiversity; Lessened the occurrences of wildfires.	Continued forest regeneration & increased forest biodiversity
<i>Equity</i>	Even distribution and recognition of responsibilities and rights regardless of gender, education, age & economic status	Enriched reciprocity & collective labor
<i>Other Impacts</i>	Culture: Enriched IKSP & Culture Empowerment Food security & health: increased income and livelihood opportunities for families Environmental quality: Improved watershed, carbon protection, and improved biodiversity conservation	Culture: Enriched IKSP & environmental values Food security & health: more diverse protein & medicinal plant sources Environmental quality: Improved water, air, and soil quality; Increased overall biodiversity

Synthesis

The social forestry framework, as depicted by Rebugio, is a

useful framework for describing and analyzing IFMs. The two communities are relatively similar in terms of the social forestry elements based on Rebugio's framework. However, there was a growing realization that the framework can be further enhanced when looking at indigenous or traditional social forestry since cultural elements, which are significant in IP communities, are not distinctly emphasized in the framework. The social and cultural context in Rebugio's framework were collectively included in the environmental element. To give an example, the two traditional technologies mentioned, such as the FIT for KEF and the *muyong* for the Ifugaos, portray huge similarities with today's scientific methods, specifically in Silviculture and Agroforestry. Yet there is a rising question on what has driven the success of these traditional methods that lacked or even failed in modern and today's applications. In addition, Rebugio's social forestry framework appears to apply more appropriately to social forestry as an intervention system rather than as an embedded part of a community, which is the case for IFMs as social forestry systems. As illustrated in the IFM cases, the indigenous social forestry systems emanate from culture, including values and Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP), that are enhanced through time and, hence, sustainable. The addition of culture as an element would help better understand and contextualize varying issues, problems, and specific cases unique but not limited to Indigenous communities further to understand social forestry, its processes, and development.

Non-indigenous Forest Management: Barobbob Watershed and CBFM-ITTO Context

To compare the environmental context of the Barobbob watershed and CBFM-ITTO, it can be observed that in terms of their biophysical environment, both sites fall under climatic type 3 because they are both in Nueva Vizcaya. However, their areas are incomparable because, obviously, the management unit of CBFM-ITTO is larger than the management unit of the Barobbob watershed has an area of 3,000 and 867, respectively. In terms of their land cover, Barobbob is mostly residual forest, grassland, and agricultural areas with some agroforestry areas, too. In contrast, plantations, dipterocarp forests, and

agroforestry areas dominate CBFM-ITTO. Similarly, since both are forest areas, the livelihoods of the communities in Barobbob and CBFM-ITTO were mostly forest-based.

Table 4

Comparison of Environmental Context in Barobbob Watershed and CBFM-ITTO

	Barobbob Watershed	CBFM-ITTO
Biophysical	BW has a total area of 867 ha, which is recognized as a major watershed in Nueva Vizcaya. It falls under Climate Type 3, with an average annual rainfall of 2400mm. It is largely dominated by residual forest cover, grassland, and agricultural areas.	The CBFM-ITTO has a total area of 3000 hectares, of which 1500 ha are dipterocarp forests, 1300 ha are agroforestry, and 200 ha are plantation and regenerating forests. Further, the area is a part and parcel of the Magat River basin. In terms of climate, it falls under climate Type 3.
Socio-Economic	Less than 200 families are living inside the Barobbob Watershed that are mostly engaged in forest-based livelihoods.	There are about 180 households that are members of the PO, and the majority practice forest-based livelihood.

Targets

In terms of the target system, both areas aim to protect their forest areas and provide livelihood opportunities for the community. However, they differ slightly in terms of forest management objectives, wherein Barobbob focuses on the restoration and rehabilitation of their forest areas. At the same

time, CBFM-ITTO wants to pursue forest plantation establishment. Moreover, in terms of their social targets, similarly, the social forestry interventions in Barobbob and CBFM-ITTO aim to benefit the people's organizations of officers and members primarily. The government unit, the DENR, and other institutions, such as the academe, are the indirect beneficiaries.

Table 5

Comparison of Target Systems in Barobbob Watershed and CBFM-ITTO

	Barobbob Watershed	CBFM-ITTO
Goal	To make Barobbob Watershed a model of life-sustaining resources that are managed on a sustainable basis	Improve the productivity of degraded and regenerating forest lands through community-based forest management by the application of research-validated methods.
Objectives	To restore the vegetative cover in the critically located areas of the watershed as soon as possible. To recognize the "right to stay" in the area as partners for development To strengthen the "right to stay" through community organization and awarding of tenurial instruments to each member by way of a Land Management Agreement	Establish forest plantations and manage regenerating and mature natural forests using research-validated methods; Manage forest resources through the community-based forest management (CBFM) strategy and Develop a community-level system of monitoring the criteria and indicators of sustainable forest management.

Goals and Objectives

Both sites are geared towards participatory sustainable management of their assigned areas. They aim to improve forest cover and land productivity to sustain the ecosystem goods and

services derived from it. The objectives, similar to their goals, are to restore vegetative cover by planting and managing the forest. However, their objectives differ in the emphasis on succeeding points. For the Barobbob, the emphasis is on making sure that the people get their "right to stay" in the area by partnering for development and organizing themselves into a community organization so that tenurial instruments are awarded to them. Meanwhile, in the case of CBFM-ITTO, the focus is on participatory management that would employ CBFM strategies and develop a community-level system of monitoring the criteria and indicators of sustainable forest management.

Table 6

Comparison between the Objectives of the Social Forestry Program in Barobbob Watershed and CBFM- ITTO

	Barobbob Watershed	CBFM-ITTO
Goal	To make Barobbob Watershed a model of life-sustaining resources that are managed on a sustainable basis	Improve the productivity of degraded and regenerating forest lands through community-based forest management by the application of research-validated methods.
Objectives	To restore the vegetative cover in the critically located areas of the watershed as soon as possible. To recognize the "right to stay" in the area as partners for development To strengthen the "right to stay" through community organization and awarding of tenurial instruments to each member by way of a Land Management Agreement	Establish forest plantations and manage regenerating and mature natural forests using research-validated methods; Manage forest resources through the community-based forest management (CBFM) strategy and Develop a community-level system of monitoring the criteria and indicators of sustainable forest management.

Technology

Both sites practice agroforestry. CBFM ITTO employs SALT, while BWOA employs gardening or cash crops together with forest trees. In the literature, BWOA also has oishpond on terraced areas, erosion control through planting, vegetative boundary delineation, and Abaca planting, whose planting materials are provided by DENR. Meanwhile, CBFM-ITTO is utilizing non-timber forest products, such as winemaking, for its enterprise. However, in the case of BWOA, they have the right to harvest, but mainly not for commercial purposes (Cruz et al., 2008).

Table 7

Comparison of the Technologies Employed in Barobbob Watershed and CBFM-ITTO

Barobbob Watershed	CBFM-ITTO
Agroforestry farming	Agroforestry farming
Home Gardening	Sloping Agricultural Land Technology
Fishpond on Terraced Rice Area	Non-Timber Forest Products
Erosion control and vegetative boundary delineation	Soil and Water Conservation
Abaca Planting	

Agency

Agency systems of the Barobbob watershed and the CBFM-ITTO are similar in terms of internal and external agencies. First, they are both managed by a People's Organization. The Barobbob Watershed Occupants' Association co-manages part of the Barobbob watershed. In contrast, the Federation of Vista Hills, Kalongkong, and Kakilingan Upland Farmers Association, Inc. manages the CBFM-ITTO. In terms of internal agencies, the CBFM-ITTO has a more centralized and systematic agency as it employs policies on a community-level. Thus, PO members have relatively collective interests due to the presence of a unified policy for all members. The BWOA, on the other hand, is composed of members with individual Memorandum of Agreement. Therefore, interests are expected to be scattered and differing. In terms of external support (Table 7), both POs are

receiving outside aid and assistance, both technical and financial aspects, from government agencies, academe, interest groups, and other organizations.

Table 7

Comparison of Agency Systems in Barobbob Watershed and CBFM-ITTO

	Barobbob Watershed	CBFM-ITTO
People's Organization	BWOA members managed the land parcels	The Federation of Vista Hills, Kalingong, and Kalingan Upland Farmers Inc. is managing the CBFM area.
External Support	NVSU, Bagabag Upland Free Farmers Association Inc., Philippine Rural Reconstruction Movement (PRRM), and Organization of European Community Fund (OECF)	DENR (MENRO and PENRO), Local Government Unit of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, the Academe, and initially, the ITTO.

Impacts

LIFE indicators, namely livelihood, income, forest condition, and equity, were used to determine the impacts of social forestry intervention on the two non-indigenous forest management sites. As a result, the impacts of social forestry programs in these two sites are not far from each other, owing to relatively similar systems. First, livelihood in both areas has increased and diversified. There is also the presence of livelihood systems in both sites that are not related to forests, such as construction work in the lowlands, businesses or enterprises, and other professional work. Further, the overall income has improved in both sites. However, the increase in income does not uplift their socio-economic conditions because most, if not all, households remain poor. Due to the community-based interventions employed in the sites, the forest condition likewise improved with a focus on biodiversity enhancement and conservation of natural resources, which are all evident in the

increase of wildlife and improvement of forest cover. Lastly, BWOA members gained equitable access to forest resources, enabling them to have more benefits in managing the forestland. On the other hand, the FVHKKUFAI members were able to minimize competition for natural resources due to community organizing, which maximized the local participation of the community members.

Table 8

Comparison of Impacts of Social Forestry in Barobbob Watershed and CBFM-ITTO

THEME	Barobbob Watershed	CBFM-ITTO
Livelihood	Increase in diversity of forest-based livelihood and use of land	Presence of forest-dependent but not highly detrimental livelihood opportunities
Income	Increase farmers' income but limited to a few members of the community	Improved income levels, but most still belong to low-income group
Forest Condition	Biodiversity preservation and conservation	Signioicant increase in closed-canopy and plantation forests and a decrease in cultivated and grassland areas
Equity	Increased benefits gained for managing the land	Minimized forest resource competition and maximized local participation

Synthesis

Key findings of the study reveal that the elements of Rebugio's framework were directly observed in the two non-indigenous forest management sites. With regards to the framework, both sites have their similarities. The difference is seen in the tenurial instrument that devolves to managing forest land. For CBFM- -ITTO, it is the CBFMA that they hold that ultimately uses the CBFM as a social forestry intervention. Meanwhile, the BWOA holds MOAs that grant them the "right to stay," given that they will adhere to the goals and objectives stipulated in the MOA.

It was also observed that there is a difference in the way the tenurial rights were granted. For the BWOA, although they have constituted themselves in a people's organization, the MOA was distributed among the individual members. Thus, BWOA exhibits multiple holders of MOA. It is also the reason why they were able to sell some of the rights to the land of the Barobbob watershed. In contrast, CBFM-ITTO holds only one CBFMA for

the whole federation, even though the federation itself has three different associations. They are united in goals and objectives and adhere to the rules and regulations stipulated in the agreement.

Both sites experience threats in terms of tenurial instruments. Hence, no perpetual security of tenure. For the BWOA, the renewal is threatened by the uncontrolled and rampant buying and selling of rights. In contrast, for CBFM-ITTO, the smooth renewal of their tenurial instrument is being hindered by the conflicting claims between different IPs, with some already putting their *muhon* (marker) on the ground in the areas being managed by the CBFM-ITTO.

Lastly, during the discussions, it was revealed that the PO officers of both sites were not given incentives for the work rendered. As such, accepting to be elected as officials of the organizations is almost voluntary if not for the perks of having to attend training intended for farming and livelihood as representatives of their organizations. Thus, it could also be inferred that since the services are voluntary, holding them accountable for any dispute is almost questionable.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Both indigenous and non-indigenous forest management systems demonstrated elements of social forestry based on Rebugio's framework. However, some of the elements are not explicitly and formally defined in the indigenous cases. Although the elements were less explicitly identified in the case of Ifugao and were gleaned from other existing information, the *muyong* could still be defined as a functioning social forestry system with Rebugio's interacting components (environment, goals and objectives, targets, technologies, impacts). The KEF, as an IFM, had a more interventionist character than the *muyong*. Meanwhile, as interventions, the interactions and the feedback in the non-IFM cases were observable in accordance with Rebugio's framework.

The key role of culture, especially in indigenous forest

management systems, needs to be more clearly considered in the framework (e.g., in indigenous psycho-spiritual ways of knowing and doing research, etc.). While it is understood that culture is included in the Environmental context in Rebugio's framework, it is not distinctly indicated and, hence, could not fully capture its importance in IFMs such as in the case of the Ifugao and the Ikalahan forest management systems studied.

Similarities across cases were observed in terms of utilization of agroforestry and diversification of livelihoods in the systems. Meanwhile, the IFM and non-IFM cases differed in terms of the financial incentives noted as a limitation in the non-IFM cases. In contrast, in the IFM cases, emphasis was given more on the need to maintain cultural values for the environment (passing on to the next generations) and reciprocity.

In comparing the IFMs, the Ikalahan system has been found to be more formally organized and integrated into mainstream institutions than the Ifugao *muyong*. This has both positive and negative implications: positive, in that value-adding technologies for processing non-timber forest products (e.g., jams) were considered and implemented; and negative, in that the same technologies also faced challenges in relation to supply and demand (e.g., exporting the jams was considered in the past but production has declined).

As more formally designed and implemented systems, the non-IFMs had similar characteristics in most of the elements (e.g., goals, objectives, and targets). This can be related to the systems' design based on existing policies, programs, and institutional arrangements.

There are two sides to the coin in terms of the more complex institutional arrangements in non-IFM cases. It adds to the challenges in the management system. Still, the more formalized structure may also help ensure accountability compared to informal IFM institutions, on the other if cultural values for environmental stewardship are eroded in IP communities. Another challenge in non-IFM institutions is that the regularly changing local government officials or assigned agency officers can easily influence support for or against a

particular program.

Based on the findings of the study, a framework that more clearly encapsulates the realities of social forestry in terms of the key role of culture in developing indigenous forest management systems can be developed. IFMs are less interventionist, but they are also considered social forestry systems. More explicit inclusion of culture as an important factor can better capture the realities on the ground.

Considering the similarities and differences across IFM and non-IFM cases, it is recommended that opportunities for co-learning between and among indigenous and non-indigenous social forestry systems be maximized towards enriching social forestry as a field and as a practice. Co-learning based on actual experiences can enrich forest management through social forestry, facilitate the bridging of indigenous and Western knowledge, and also help cultivate a supportive environment between IFM and non-IFM initiatives. This is important considering the existence of overlapping initiatives and conflicts over land ownership/ management, especially in ancestral domains where most forests are situated. Co-learning contributes to the learning process and can facilitate adaptation of forest management to changing contexts.

Further studies are recommended to provide a more comprehensive and in-depth analysis of IFM and non-IFM cases as social forestry systems in the Philippines. This is especially important since social forestry and community-based forest management continue to be recognized as sustainable forest management strategies/ approaches in the country. For example, indigenous non-technological practices related to psycho-spiritual socio-cultural ecosystemic realities and their implications for forest and community wellness can be further explored in future studies. A deep personal connection with nature has been found in studies to be important in influencing environmental worldviews and human-environment relationships. Developing and capitalizing on spiritual/ cultural connections with nature and non-technological practices that also improve forest conditions and community well-being is still relevant, especially amid current wellness trends that emphasize

spiritual, emotional, and cultural aspects.

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